

Research on figure description sentences recognition of academic full text based on pre-training language model

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Introduction

Text Classification is an important application in natural language processing and plays a key role in text information processing. In the past few years, due to the unprecedented success of deep learning research, the research on text classification using deep learning methods has increased dramatically and achieved good results. For example, Bert (Devlin et al., 2018) has achieved significant breakthroughs in various NLP tasks by training on large-scale unlabeled text resources. FinBert (Yang et al., 2020) was the first Chinese pre-training language model in the financial field, and its results had been significantly improved in such tasks as Short Message Classification, Emotion Classification and Named Entity Recognition in the financial domain. In academia, SciBERT (Beltagy et al., 2019) performed unsupervised pre-training on a large corpus of multi-domain academic publications to improve the performance on academic NLP tasks and achieved state-of-the-art results on tasks such as Text Classification and Named Entity Recognition. In recent years, the research of academic full text has attracted wide attention. Extracting specific types of sentences from texts, such as research method sentences, research results sentences and figure description sentences, has become an important research content of academic full text. Therefore, in this research, Journal_bert, Journal_scibert, and Journal_roberta models were applied to recognize figure description sentences in academic full text.

Data and Method

Data

Data for this research was collected from the Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology (JASIST), SAGE Journals, Journal of Enterprise Information Management (JIIM), Journal of Knowledge Management (JKM), and Scientometrics during the period 2010-2022. A total of 6,666 articles constitutes the corpus of this experiment.

There are 446 JASIST articles, 547 SAGE articles, 550 JIIM articles, 1,033 JKM articles, and 4,090 Scientometrics articles.

Method

In this work, FD (Figure Description) was used to label figure descriptions sentences, and O (Ordinary) was used to label Non-FD sentences.

In this paper, we used three pre-trained language models Journal_bert, Journal_scibert and Journal_roberta to recognize figure description sentences in full text of JASIST, SAGE, JIIM, JKM and Scientometrics. The above three models were pre-trained based on bert-base-cased, scibert_scivocab_cased and hfroberta using a total of 8481 papers in the library and information science domain, respectively.

Result

The experiment first used the data of JASIST and SAGE to form the corpus for training, but the recognition results of the three models were not ideal. Therefore, in the second stage, we expanded the data scale and used a total of 6,666 papers from 5 journals to form the final academic full text corpus. We randomly shuffled the corpus order and divided the corpus according to the training set: test set =9:1 and used the F-value and Macro-AVG F-value to evaluate the recognition effect of the models. The summarized results are shown in Table 1. The values of the hyperparameters set in the experiment are as follows: maximum sequence length 512, batch size 16, learning rate 0.00002, epoch 3.0.

Table 1. Summarized Results

Pre-Model	FD F-value	O F-value	Macro Avg F-value
Journal_bert	98.33%	99.88%	91.07%
Journal_scibert	98.59%	99.90%	91.41%
Journal_roberta	97.90%	99.86%	91.12%

In general, Journal_bert, Journal_scibert and Journal_roberta were all able to recognize figure

description sentences from academic full text exceedingly well.

And the results of Journal_scibert model were superior to Journal_bert model and Journal_roberta model from F-value or Macro Avg F-value. The scale of figure description sentences in this experimental corpus is relatively small. We plan to continue to expand the scale of corpus and translate figure description sentences into Chinese, Cantonese, Korean, Japanese, etc., with the help of translation tools, and then translate the results back to English to expand the proportion of figure description sentences.

Conclusions

In this research, an academic full text corpus was constructed based on the data of 5 international journals in the library and information science, and Journal_bert, Journal_scibert and Journal_roberta were used to recognize figure description sentences from academic full text, respectively.

Our work provides ideas for the recognition of figure description sentences in academic full text research. Further, according to the experimental results, cluster analysis and keyword topic recognition can be conducted for figure description sentences, so as to understand the intrinsic characteristics of figure description sentences at a more micro level.

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